

From Entropy Dynamics of Neuronal Coherence to Valenced Percepts: A Topos-Theoretic Construction

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Abstract

We develop a theory of neural organization in which percepts are modeled as probabilistic structures on directed acyclic graphs of time-stamped subthreshold oscillatory states, and affective valence is defined by entropy dynamics on these structures. Each graph is assigned two pattern functors: a bound functor, whose elements are Bayesian networks compatible with the graph's causal organization, and an unbound functor, whose elements are arbitrary distributions on the corresponding vertex-state spaces. These functors are organized in a set-valued presheaf topos over the category of directed acyclic graphs with ancestral inclusions, so that restriction corresponds to marginalization. Within this setting, percept-types are subfunctors, percepts are compatible families of local distributions, and the entropic valence determines a time-dependent Grothendieck topology governing which local patterns count as admissible for perceptual integration. The resulting internal intuitionistic logic provides a formal language for describing local endorsement, obstruction, and amalgamation of perceptual structure. We argue that this framework gives a principled account of how perceptual coherence and affective valence may jointly arise from mesoscopic cortical field dynamics.

Keywords: theoretical neuroscience, consciousness, valence, topos theory, entropy, Bayesian networks

1. Introduction

The first part of this paper focuses primarily on the mathematical aspects of the theory, developing the ideas proposed in Cacioppo (2025). Neurobiological interpretations are initially introduced only insofar as they clarify the purpose of the mathematics, with more thorough interpretations presented in later sections.

1.1. The Base Category \mathbb{D}

A *stage* is a directed acyclic graph (DAG) $D = (V, E)$ with vertices $\iota = (i, t_{i_k}) \in V$ and edge set E . A directed edge can extend from vertex (i, t_{i_k}) to vertex (j, t_{j_l}) only if $t_{i_k} < t_{j_l}$.² The set of vertices in D is denoted variously by V , $V(D)$, or simply D . The stage represents a spatiotemporal snapshot of activity in an ensemble of cortical intratelencephalic (IT) pyramidal neurons, with each vertex $\iota = (i, t_{i_k})$ encoding the subthreshold state of neuron i at relative time t_{i_k} . We take the *STO state space* for IT neuron i at time t_{i_k} to be Σ_i , the set of possible subthreshold oscillation (STO) states s_i for neuron i at t_{i_k} , and $\Sigma_D = \prod_{\iota \in D} \Sigma_\iota$ is the *joint STO state space* for stage D , which contains all possible joint configurations $s_D = (s_\iota)_{\iota \in D}$.³ A joint distribution p_D

on the joint state space Σ_D is called *unstructured*, unless it is also a Bayesian network on D , in which case it is called *structured*.

We define the base category \mathbb{D} for the presheaf topos $\text{Sets}^{\mathbb{D}^{\text{op}}}$ as follows: objects are nonempty finite vertex-labeled DAGs with at most one edge between any two vertices, and morphisms are ancestral inclusions, denoted by \leq . Its opposite category, \mathbb{D}^{op} , defines morphisms as restriction to an ancestral subDAG, which will be called a *substage of D* . The restriction of a distribution p_D on stage D to a substage D' is defined by marginalization: $p_{D'} = (p_D)|_{D'}$. We note that the restriction of a structured distribution on a stage is a structured distribution on any substage since Markov factorization is inherited by ancestrally closed subDAGs.

Thus, we can define the *bound functor* F and the *unbound functor* F° , from $\mathbb{D}^{\text{op}} \rightarrow \text{Sets}$, which assign to each stage D the set of structured distributions and the set of unstructured distributions on D , respectively. Additional background information is in Supplementary Material, Section 1.

1.2. STO Coherency in Stage D

For a distribution p_D on stage D , either structured or unstructured, let $p_\iota = (p_D)|_\iota$. The informational correlation between the component states s_ι of the joint state s is

$$C_{p_D}(s) := \log \frac{p_D(s)}{\prod_{\iota \in D} p_\iota(s_\iota)}. \quad (1)$$

Positive/negative correlation between the components s_ι of s indicates a greater/smaller probability for s than if the component states were independent. The *total coherency* $\text{TC}(p_D)$ of

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²The double subscript will allow for a neuron to appear multiple times within a stage, representing feedback or recurrent participation within the stage.

³The subscript D in Σ_D and s_D may be suppressed when the stage is understood.

this distribution on D is defined as the expectation of C_{p_D} with respect to p_D ,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TC}(p_D) &:= \mathbb{E}_{p_D}[C_{p_D}] = \sum_s p_D(s) \log \frac{p_D(s)}{\prod_{i \in D} p_i(s_i)} \\ &= D_{\text{KL}}(p_D \parallel \prod_{i \in D} p_i) \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where D_{KL} is the Kullback-Leibler divergence. This yields the following relationship between total coherency and the Shannon entropy H for p_D :

$$H(p_D) = \sum_{i \in D} H(p_i) - \text{TC}(p_D), \quad (3)$$

which expresses entropy as cumulative nodal dispersion minus total stage coherency.

On stage D , let u denote the constant, uniform, max entropy distribution on the joint state space Σ for D , $|\Sigma| = N$. Then we also have

$$H(p_D) = \log N - D_{\text{KL}}(p_D \parallel u). \quad (4)$$

1.3. Percept-Types, Percepts, and Handles

Let δ denote a downward closed subcategory of \mathbb{D} . A *percept-type* is a subfunctor P_δ of either the bound functor F or the unbound functor F° that maps stages outside of δ to the empty set. If P_δ is a percept-type then a *percept of type P_δ on stage $D \in \delta$* is a natural transformation from a sieve S_D on D to P_δ . Since \mathbb{D} is a thin category, we can represent a sieve on D as a downward closed collection of substages of D . More simply then, this percept is a family $S(p_i)$ of compatible distributions p_i on each stage D_i in S such that each $p_i \in P_\delta(D_i)$. A percept-type or percept may be called structured or unstructured, depending on if P_δ is a subfunctor of F or F° , respectively. Neurobiologically, a percept-type P_δ is interpreted as a constraint on percepts on stages within the cortical boundary specified by δ , implemented through intrinsic or learned circuit parameters.

Sparse codes for percepts and percept-types are referred to as *handles*. They serve as proxies for underlying realizations and enable subsequent approximate reconstruction. We propose that the logic using the operations of a Heyting algebra of sieve-valued truth states is performed in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (dlPFC), with percept-type handles serving as operands. This greatly enlarges the expressive range of percept-types by forming logical expressions of percept-type handles that can be fully expressed as a percept-type in association or premotor cortices. A time-varying Grothendieck topology modulates the semantics of this logic, shifting the system dynamically between more intuitionistic and more Boolean regimes. This logical reasoning is modeled at the level of semantic constraint manipulation rather than syntactic proof construction. We take syntactic proof constructions to belong to the metatheory, not to the cognitive mechanism itself.⁴

⁴Assuming the Kripke-Joyal interpretation, the results of these constraint manipulations are compatible with the standard proof rules of intuitionistic higher-order logic.

1.4. Amalgamations of a Percept

Let $S(p_i)$ be a percept on stage D . This is a compatible family of distributions p_i on each $D_i \in S$. Let E be any stage covered by the family $\{D_i\}$ in the current topology. Then, a distribution p_E on E that restricts to each distribution p_i is called an *amalgamation of $S(p_i)$* .

2. The Entropy-Valence Postulate

The joint state space Σ for stage D contains mesoscopic states of STO oscillations (tens to hundreds of milliseconds) that coarse-grain microscopic trajectories (0.5 to 5 ms) to average out noise but retain relatively stable parameters. The time-dependent distribution on D is denoted p_D^t and the subsequent distribution on D is denoted $p_D^{t+\Delta t}$ where Δt is the time to establish the later distribution $p_D^{t+\Delta t}$.

We postulate a scalar-valued physical dynamic quantity, which we call *valence*, accompanied by a primitive, structureless, and contentless subjective state called *hedonic tone*. The postulated association is that a positive valence is associated with positive hedonic tone, a negative valence with negative hedonic tone, and zero valence with the absence of hedonic tone. The magnitude of valence indicates the intensity of its hedonic tone.

The valence $v_D^{t+\Delta t}$ generated at stage D by the transition from p_D^t to $p_D^{t+\Delta t}$ is defined to be

$$v_D^{t+\Delta t} := -\frac{H(p_D^{t+\Delta t}) - H(p_D^t)}{\Delta t}. \quad (5)$$

From equation (3), valence can be expressed as the rate of change of total coherency minus the cumulative rate of change of the nodal dispersions on D , and from equation (4), it is also the rate at which the distribution is moving toward or away from the uniform distribution on D . The valence formula is independent of whether the distribution p_D is structured or not.

2.1. Optimal Distributions for Intense Valence

The interval Δt is the time required to establish the later distribution $p_D^{t+\Delta t}$, which in turn requires the stabilization of mesoscopic STO states. This stabilization time is expected to be longer for structured distributions because structured distributions must additionally express Markov factorization over the edges of the stage D . So, by equation (5), for a given entropy change, unstructured distributions on a stage with edges may generate larger valence intensities than structured distributions.

At the opposite extreme, consider a stage D with no edges, so we can assume the stabilization time is approximately the same whether the distribution is structured or not. If the distribution p_D is structured, then Markov factorization gives $p_D = \prod_{i \in D} p_i$ and the total coherence remains zero for both earlier and later distributions. By Section 1.2,

$$v_D = -\frac{\Delta H(p_D)}{\Delta t} = -\sum_{i \in D} \frac{\Delta H(p_i)}{\Delta t}. \quad (6)$$

Therefore, achieving valence with a large magnitude requires coordinated, unidirectional changes across many independent node distributions.

If, instead, p_D is unstructured, then

$$v_D = \frac{\Delta \text{TC}(p_D)}{\Delta t} - \sum_{i \in D} \frac{\Delta H(p_i)}{\Delta t}. \quad (7)$$

In this case, changes in coherency provide an additional degree of freedom for increasing the magnitude of valence, even on an edgeless stage.

This suggests that valence of unstructured distributions is generally capable of attaining greater intensity than valence of structured distributions. We will associate valence of unstructured distributions with subjective states such as pain and pleasure (Section 4.3), which implies these subjective states can have greater intensities than with valence of structured distributions. We suggest that valence of unstructured distributions typically occur in agranular cortices, whereas valence of structured distributions are more naturally supported by granular cortex, which has a dedicated layer 4 for more structured integration of inputs. The evolutionary origins of the agranular cortex trace back to the ancient three-layered amniote brain with the granular cortex appearing much later.

3. Valence Modulates Topology

Remnants of these early agranular and dysgranular cortical structures exist in the human brain, collectively known as the limbic cortex. Since IT neurons are assumed to produce valence, and IT neurons occur throughout the cortex, we presume valence would also be generated cortex-wide. Because limbic valence is hypothesized to be from unstructured distributions that are evolutionarily early and intense, we attribute to it the generation of the temporally changing topology on the base category. This topology will be imposed on the entire cortex; in particular, on the stages in the association cortices, affecting the amalgamations of structured percepts in the association cortices.

Definition 1. A *Grothendieck topology* on the base category \mathbb{D} is an assignment to each stage D , a set $J(D)$ of sieves on D such that the mapping J satisfies three axioms: maximality, stability, and transitivity (Supplementary Material, Section 2). The sieves in $J(D)$ are called *J-covers* for D . A topology J is *finer* than topology J' if for each stage D , $J'(D) \subseteq J(D)$.

3.1. The Default Topology

The topology in the absence of limbic valence is chosen to represent a natural and neutral notion of cover, the *joint-cover topology*, where a family of substages D_i of stage D covers D if $\bigvee_i D_i = D$, their spatiotemporal join. We note that any join of stages along common vertices is again a stage (acyclicity is assured by the assumption that edges always point to a later time) and each D_i is a substage of their join. Some of the characteristics of this topology are:

1. the set of truth values at stage D is $\{\downarrow D' \mid D' \text{ is a substage of } D\}$;
2. the internal logic is intuitionistic; in particular, the law of excluded middle may fail.

To account for differences in behavior due to hedonic tone, we propose that increasingly negative valence produces increasingly coarse topologies and increasingly positive valence produces increasingly finer topologies. As the topology becomes finer, the number of truth values — the sieves in $\Omega_J(D)$ — decreases, lowering the threshold for satisfaction of percept-type constraints. Simultaneously, the number of covers increases, creating more opportunities for an amalgamation. Taken together, these effects imply that a finer topology increases the opportunities for property-preserving amalgamation. These effects are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

3.2. Valence-Modulated Topologies via Valence Cores

We consider a natural way to define finer topologies than J_{joint} in the presence of positive valence, and coarser topologies than J_{joint} when valence is negative.

3.2.1. The valence core C_v in \mathbb{D}

Definition 2. A *valence core* $C_v(D) \subseteq V(D)$, defined for each valence v and for each $D \in \mathbb{D}$, has the following properties: for every $v, v' \in \mathbb{R}$ and $D, D' \in \mathbb{D}$,

1. identity for $v = 0$: $C_0(D) = V(D)$,
2. antitone for $v \geq 0$: if $0 \leq v' \leq v$ then $C_{v'}(D) \supseteq C_v(D)$,
3. antitone for $v < 0$: if $v' \leq v < 0$ then $C_{v'}(D) \supseteq C_v(D)$, and
4. functorial: if D' is a substage of D , then $C_v(D') = V(D') \cap C_v(D)$.

The limbic valence would determine the topology by establishing the valence cores throughout the cortex. We propose that these cores define the topology used to realize percept-types and percept amalgamations.

3.2.2. Valence modulation: toward a finer or coarser topology

Definition 3. 1. Let $v \geq 0$. For each $D \in \mathbb{D}$, $K_v(D)$ is the collection of families \mathcal{F} of substages D' of D such that $V(\bigvee_{D' \in \mathcal{F}} D') \supseteq C_v(D)$.

2. Let $v < 0$. For each $D \in \mathbb{D}$, $K_v(D)$ is the collection of families \mathcal{F} of substages D' of D such that $\bigvee_{D' \in \mathcal{F}} D' = D$ and for each $D' \in \mathcal{F}$, $V(D') \supseteq C_v(D)$.

If $v \geq 0$, then $K_v(D)$ consists of the families $\{D_i\}_{i \in I}$ of substages of D whose vertices collectively cover the valence core of D . Thus, positive valence relaxes the joint-cover condition: a family need only cover the core $C_v(D)$, not necessarily all of D . If $v < 0$, then $K_v(D)$ consists of the families $\{D_i\}_{i \in I}$ of substages of D whose join is D and whose individual members each contain the valence core of D . Thus, negative valence strengthens the joint-cover condition: the family must cover all of D , and every member must contain the core $C_v(D)$.

Theorem 1. For all v , K_v is a basis for a Grothendieck topology.

Table 1: Effects as the Grothendieck topology becomes finer

Covering families	Sheaf condition	Set of sheaves	Local covers	Truth values	Resolution
Increase	Harder	Shrinks	Increases	Shrinks	Decreases

Table 2: Summary of valence effects on the Grothendieck topology

Valence	Topology	Resolution by truth values	Logic	Experience
$\nu < 0$	coarser (less gluing possible)	high-resolution	“everything is different”	threat-based, opposed to change
$\nu > 0$	finer (more gluing possible)	low-resolution	“everything is the same”	reward-based, open to change

A proof is given in Supplementary Material, Section 3.

A basis K generates a Grothendieck topology J by defining $J(D)$ to be the collection of all sieves on D that contain a member of $K(D)$.

Definition 4. For all ν , J_ν is the Grothendieck topology generated by the basis K_ν .

The following observations follow easily:

1. J_0 is the joint-cover topology, hence in the absence of valence, the default topology is the joint-cover topology,⁵ and
2. for all ν', ν , if $\nu' < \nu$ then $J_{\nu'}$ is coarser than, or equal to, J_ν .

3.2.3. Example of a valence core

Let D be an arbitrary stage in \mathbb{D} . Recall that a vertex $\iota = (i, t_{i_k})$ of D represents neuron i at time t_{i_k} . Let $d(\iota)$ be a measure of the connectivity of neuron i at time t_{i_k} with other neurons; here, we let $d(\iota)$ be the total synaptic input strength from IT neurons to IT neuron i at time t_{i_k} . Define the *relevant vertices* $R_\nu(D)$ in stage D ,

$$R_\nu(D) := \{\iota \in V(D) \mid d(\iota) \geq \mu(|\nu|)\},$$

where μ is a strictly increasing function with $\mu(0) = 0$.

$R_\nu(D)$ is the subset of vertices ι at stage D where $d(\iota)$ is at least as large as $\mu(|\nu|)$, which can be interpreted as an approximate identification of the neurons within that stage most responsible for contributing, either directly or indirectly, to the current limbic valence. In an environment of positive hedonic tone, $\nu > 0$, prioritizing the role of the vertices in $R_\nu(D)$ at stage D (through the topology induced by the core C_ν) might increase the possibility of attaining even greater valence. In contrast, in the presence of negative hedonic tone, $\nu < 0$, the system avoids $R_\nu(D)$ (again, through the induced topology), with the possibility of avoiding even lower valence. Thus we define the core

$C_\nu(D)$ as follows:

$$C_\nu(D) := \begin{cases} R_\nu(D) & \text{when } \nu > 0, \\ V(D) & \text{when } \nu = 0, \text{ and} \\ V(D) \setminus R_\nu(D) & \text{when } \nu < 0. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

It is easily verified that C_ν is a valence core. Intuitively, the positive valence core *includes* the valence-responsible regions of D , while the negative valence core *excludes* the valence-responsible regions of D . In this example, as ν increases in either interval, $(-\infty, 0)$ or $[0, \infty)$, $C_\nu(D)$ decreases from $V(D)$ to \emptyset .

3.3. Summary of Valence Operational Effects

Hedonic neutrality corresponds to the joint-cover topology. As hedonic tone becomes more negative, the topology becomes coarser; as hedonic tone becomes more positive, the topology becomes finer. A coarser topology has more truth values and fewer covers, giving higher resolution but fewer opportunities for amalgamation, and the system enters a more rigid, differentiated state. A finer topology has fewer truth values and more covers, giving lower resolution but more opportunities for amalgamation, and the system moves toward a more unified, integrative state.

3.3.1. The Impact of Topology on Amalgamations

The sheaf property is the strongest amalgamation condition for a percept-type. It is topology-dependent.

Theorem 2. The bound functor $F : \mathbb{D}^{\text{op}} \rightarrow \text{Sets}$, where $F(D)$ is the set of structured distributions on D , is a sheaf in the joint-cover topology J on \mathbb{D} . Hence, it is also a sheaf in any coarser topology.

A proof is given in Supplementary Material, Section 8.

However, for topologies finer than the default topology, all three possibilities exist: amalgamations may exist for some covers but not others, and when they do exist, they may not be unique.

The situation is more delicate for unstructured percept-types since the unbound functor F° of unstructured distributions is not a sheaf in the default topology. Nonetheless, even with

⁵Since each D' is ancestrally closed in D , $V(\bigvee_{D' \in \mathcal{F}} D') = V(D) \Leftrightarrow \bigvee_{D' \in \mathcal{F}} D' = D$.

unstructured percepts, as long as we maintain a topology at least as coarse as the default topology, and consider *simultaneous* realization of the percept, a unique amalgamation exists for the percept on the covered stage. However, this can fail even on these coarser topologies when the amalgamation is for a percept-handle, since the handle specifications need to be realized simultaneously, which would prevent an amalgamation if there is an obstruction to the existence of a joint distribution.

The topology also affects the preservation of a percept's characteristics after an amalgamation. For an internally described percept-type, the topology J affects which distributions belong to it at each stage by specifying constraining characteristics. For instance, if the unstructured percept-type A is defined by a formula $\varphi(p)$ with free variable p that denotes a distribution, then the J -interpreted percept-type is

$$A_J(D) := \{ p_D \in F^\circ(D) \mid D \Vdash_J \varphi(p_D) \}; \quad (9)$$

see Supplementary Material, Section 7, for the definition of the forcing relation \Vdash_J . Thus, different choices of J may yield different stagewise extensions $A_J(D)$, even for the same syntactic formula φ .

This is distinguished from an ordinary stagewise property $A \subseteq F^\circ$ fixed externally as a subfunctor. In this case, changing J does not change A itself, but it still changes the corresponding J -forced extension A_J as given in (9). Thus, if A is not closed under the topology J , one may have $p_D \in A_J(D) \setminus A(D)$. In that case, J -forcing expresses local endorsement of A , not ordinary stagewise membership in A .

3.3.2. The Effect of Topology on Underdetermined Decision-Making

A decision can be expressed as the realization of a witness p_D for a percept-type specified by a formula φ , on a specified stage D . We call D the *decision stage* for φ . One example is a premotor decision for activation of a skeletal muscle, where φ specifies the relevant percept-type and the decision stage D lies in premotor or related cortex. If $D \Vdash_J \varphi(p_D)$, then a joint STO state $s_D \in \Sigma_D$ occurs with probability $p_D(s_D)$. Since the components of s_D are subthreshold oscillatory states, the resulting activity may or may not trigger action potentials and movement, depending on how IT neurons at this stage influence extratelencephalic pyramidal neurons. More generally, the model treats decisions throughout the cortex in the same manner: a witness p_D is constructed for a percept-type at a specified decision stage, producing an action/perception $s_D \in \Sigma_D$. Lifshitz et al. (2026) have shown in their work with zebrafish that decision-making in social behavior incorporates a distributed, coordinated pallial state rather than from a single reflex pathway or isolated social center. Their results are consistent with the view that decision stages for complex behaviors are not isolated reflex loci, but are embedded in broader telencephalic networks. In the present framework, this suggests that more complex percept-types may require decision stages with broader connectivity to telencephalic regions.

The construction of a witness p_D for a percept-type specified by φ is strongly influenced by the current topology, since

satisfaction of φ is determined by topological forcing (Supplementary Material, Sections 4, 5, and 7). Forcing becomes more permissive as the topology becomes finer, facilitating the construction of witnesses. This predicts that, other factors being equal, decisions are more easily made in a finer topology than in a coarser one.

Among Grothendieck topologies on \mathbb{D} , the dense topology (defined in Supplementary Material, Section 6) is the coarsest topology whose associated sheaf topos has Boolean internal logic. Thus, the law of excluded middle fails in the default topology J_{joint} of zero valence, which is coarser than the dense topology. A strictly intuitionistic topology, such as J_{joint} , introduces an additional indeterminacy into decision-making: neither φ nor $\neg\varphi$ need be true at the decision stage. In addition, a coarser topology has more truth values, increasing the complexity of arriving at a witness p_D whose truth value is sufficiently decisive at stage D , in the sense that $D \Vdash_J \varphi(p_D)$. In this model, a decision entails the production of an action/perception $s_D \in \Sigma_D$ that is constrained by such a witness. The model therefore predicts that topological conditions modulate the difficulty of decision formation: decisions become more difficult as hedonic tone decreases and easier as hedonic tone increases, an effect consistent with numerous studies (Isen, 2001; Werner et al., 2009).

If neither φ nor $\neg\varphi$ can be satisfied at the decision stage, the system has two options: it may use a different percept-type so that one of the alternatives can be witnessed in the current topology, or move to a finer topology through an increase in valence. In the dense topology and any finer topology, the internal logic is Boolean and the law of excluded middle holds. Thus, in a Boolean topology, for a fixed interpretation of all parameters appearing in φ , either $D \Vdash \varphi$ or $D \Vdash \neg\varphi$. Although this facilitates decision formation, witness construction remains underdetermined. Even if the microscopic dynamics is deterministic, the constraint condition specified by the percept-type is mesoscopic and need not admit a unique witness p_D , nor a unique perception/action, which is only constrained by p_D . Thus, perceived freedom in decision-making is at the level of effectively underdetermined mesoscopic dynamics, not at the level of determined or random microscopic dynamics.

4. Valenced Percepts and Consciousness

Percepts evolve over time through amalgamation, fragmentation, and natural transformations, together with the incorporation of new sensory information.

4.1. Percept-Type States

Let \mathcal{P}^t denote the active percept-types at time t . For $A \in \mathcal{P}^t$, let \mathcal{A}^t denote the A -state at time t , defined by

$$\mathcal{A}^t := \{(D, p_D^t) \mid p_D^t \in A(D)\}. \quad (10)$$

This specifies the cortical region actively processing percept-type A (recall Section 1.3). Since A is a subfunctor of F or F° , \mathcal{A}^t is a union of principal A -percepts. In general, distinct percepts need not be compatible; in this case, however, they are

compatible because they are assumed to be realized simultaneously.

The *realized state at time t* is defined by $\mathcal{R}^t = \bigcup_{A \in \mathcal{P}^t} \mathcal{A}^t$. By simultaneous realization, this is also a union of compatible percepts. We assume that the stages in the realized state cover the same valence-producing cortical region at each time t .

We now define a subfamily of \mathcal{A}^t that generates it. Let (D, p'_D) and (E, p'_E) be elements of \mathcal{A}^t . We write $(D, p'_D) \leq_A (E, p'_E)$ if $D \leq E$ and $(p'_E)|_D = p'_D$. By simultaneous realization, the condition $(p'_E)|_D = p'_D$ is always satisfied. Let

$$B'_A := \{(D, p'_D) \in \mathcal{A}^t \mid (D, p'_D) \text{ is maximal in } (\mathcal{A}^t, \leq_A)\}. \quad (11)$$

We call B'_A the *generating basis*⁶ for the A -state at time t , and denote its index set by I'_A . Thus, B'_A consists of the apexes of the maximal principal A -percepts at time t . The full A -state is obtained by closing B'_A under substages:

$$\mathcal{A}^t = \{(W, p'_W) \mid \exists (D, p'_D) \in B'_A \text{ with } W \leq D \text{ and } p'_W = (p'_D)|_W\}.$$

The *basis for \mathcal{R}^t* is defined to be $B^t := \bigcup_{A \in \mathcal{P}^t} B'_A$, indexed by $I^t := \bigcup_{A \in \mathcal{P}^t} I'_A$.

The topology J influences this basis. If A is J -closed and simultaneously realized A -witnesses on a J -cover of D admit an amalgamation $p_D \in F(D)$, then $p_D \in A(D)$. Thus, generally, an A -percept can be amalgamated into a principal A -percept whenever the relevant witnesses are compatible, an amalgamation exists, and the property A is preserved by the topology.

4.2. Valence Field

The valence field at time $t + \Delta t$ is generated by comparing the realized bases B^t and $B^{t+\Delta t}$. For simplicity, we take the next time step to be $t + \Delta t$ for the entire cortex; the construction is analogous if the time increment is region-dependent. To identify the valences produced by entropy changes in realized distributions from time t to time $t + \Delta t$, we compare the stages in the two bases B^t and $B^{t+\Delta t}$ using the family of nonempty vertex intersections. If $(D_i, p'_{D_i}) \in B^t$ and $(E_j, p'_{E_j}) \in B^{t+\Delta t}$, define

$$\begin{aligned} V_{ij} &:= V(D_i) \cap V(E_j) \\ I^{t,t+\Delta t} &:= \{(i, j) \in I^t \times I^{t+\Delta t} \mid V_{ij} \neq \emptyset\}. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Thus, the relevant family of nonempty vertex intersections is $\{V_{ij}\}_{(i,j) \in I^{t,t+\Delta t}}$.

The sets V_{ij} are not treated as stages; they serve only as domains on which distributions can be compared across time. Let p'_{ij} and $p'^{t+\Delta t}_{ij}$ denote the marginalizations of p'_{D_i} and $p'^{t+\Delta t}_{E_j}$ to V_{ij} , respectively. These are the earlier and later realized distributions on V_{ij} at times t and $t + \Delta t$. The valence v_{ij} on each V_{ij} produced by the transition from t to $t + \Delta t$ is then

$$v_{ij} = -\frac{H(p'^{t+\Delta t}_{ij}) - H(p'_{ij})}{\Delta t}. \quad (13)$$

⁶Here “basis” means a generating family for \mathcal{A}^t , not a basis for a Grothendieck topology.

There may be other members of B^t and $B^{t+\Delta t}$ whose vertex intersection is also V_{ij} , but the marginalized distributions are the same by compatibility among the members of B^t and among the members of $B^{t+\Delta t}$, which follows from simultaneous realization at each time. Hence, the valence v_{ij} is well-defined: it has the same value regardless of which members of B^t and $B^{t+\Delta t}$ are chosen to compute it. This defines *the valence field at time $t + \Delta t$ across the cortex*:

$$\mathcal{V}^{t+\Delta t} := \{(V_{ij}, v_{ij})\}_{(i,j) \in I^{t,t+\Delta t}}. \quad (14)$$

4.3. Valenced Percepts

Let (D, p'_D) be any member of the basis B^t . For each substage E of D , define Q'_E to be the *captured valences v_{ij} from the valence-field \mathcal{V}^t at this substage*,

$$Q'_E := \{v_{ij} \mid (V_{ij}, v_{ij}) \in \mathcal{V}^t \text{ and } V_{ij} \subseteq V(E)\}. \quad (15)$$

Definition 5. The *valenced percept* $\hat{Q}'_D(p)$ corresponding to $(D, p'_D) \in B^t$ is the mapping⁷

$$\hat{Q}'_D(p) : E \mapsto (p'_E, Q'_E) \quad \text{for each } E \leq D.$$

We note that $p'_E = (p'_D)|_E$. Since $Q'_{E'} \subseteq Q'_E$ whenever $E' \leq E$, $\hat{Q}'_D(p)$ is a filtration on $\downarrow D$. Some Q'_E may be the empty set if no valence-field domain V_{ij} is contained in $V(E)$.

The valenced percept $\hat{Q}'_D(p)$ depends on scalar valence values generated by earlier and later distributions on the vertex intersections lying within each substage of D , hence on the principal-sieve structure of D , which is determined by its edge structure.

This structure exists even when distributions are unstructured and D is edgeless. For a fixed vertex set, as the number of edges in D decreases, the number of substages in the principal sieve $\downarrow D$ generally increases. This may seem counterintuitive if edge structure is taken to be the source of structure in a valenced percept. However, it suggests greater uniformity and more cumulative hedonic tone in the subjective experience of a valenced percept with few edges, and a more relational subjective experience in a valenced percept with many edges. Moreover, the same unstructured distribution on two stages with the same vertex set but different edge structures gives rise to different valenced percepts, since the associated principal sieve structures are different.

If there are no entropy changes on any overlap $V_{ij} \subseteq V(E)$ for any $E \leq D$, every valence v_{ij} from the valence field captured by $\hat{Q}'_D(p)$ has value zero, denoted $\hat{Q}'_D(p) = \hat{0}$. In this case, every captured valence in the valenced percept has zero intensity, so it is not a realized subjective experience.

Hence, a valenced percept is a hierarchy of substage subjective experiences $(E, p'_E, Q'_E)_{E \leq D}$.

- Hierarchical structure: principal sieve $\downarrow D$ of substages of D

⁷Indices on p'_D are suppressed in $\hat{Q}'_D(p)$ since that information is already present in the notation.

- **Quality:** the marginal probability distributions $p_E^t = (p_D^t)_E$ on the joint STO state space Σ_E for each substage E of D
- **Hedonic tones:** sets of captured valences Q_E^t at each substage E of D

If our assumption that valence is hedonic tone is correct then a valenced percept is a hierarchical subjective experience of momentary hedonic tones, temporally ordered by substages of an IT neural activity pattern that is described by a distribution on their joint STO state. The subjective component of a valenced percept derives from the captured hedonic tones from the valence field. Its hierarchical structure and quality, derived from $\downarrow D$ and p_D^t , respectively, are objective. But the hierarchical structure and quality shape the hedonic tones to produce a higher-dimensional sensation than simple valence. For economy of terminology, and because a valenced percept is intended to model a structured unit of subjective experience, we refer to a valenced percept in this framework as a *quale*.

4.4. Connected Qualia

We now define a notion of connectedness among qualia at time t .

A collection of qualia $\{\hat{Q}_{D_\alpha}^t(p_\alpha)\}$ is *connected* if, for any two members $\hat{Q}_{D_{\alpha'}}^t(p_{\alpha'})$ and $\hat{Q}_{D_{\alpha''}}^t(p_{\alpha''})$, there exists a sequence

$$\hat{Q}_{D_{\alpha'}}^t(p_{\alpha'}) = \hat{Q}_{D_{\alpha_1}}^t(p_{\alpha_1}), \dots, \hat{Q}_{D_{\alpha_n}}^t(p_{\alpha_n}) = \hat{Q}_{D_{\alpha''}}^t(p_{\alpha''}) \quad (16)$$

from the collection such that consecutive elements share a substage D_β for which $Q_{D_\beta}^t$ contains a nonzero valence. This partitions the basis B^t into qualia-connected components C_λ^t .

However, the STO dynamics of distinct components may still be coupled through global, non-IT influences. Thus, inter-component influences that affect STO coherency between different components C_λ^t must also be taken into account.

Define a weighted graph G^t whose vertices are the qualia-connected components C_λ^t . For distinct components C_λ^t and C_μ^t , an edge is present when inter-component STO coherency exceeds the threshold required for functional coupling, and the edge weight $w_{\lambda\mu}^t$ measures the strength of that coupling. A *qualia-state at time t* is a connected component of G^t , denoted by $C_{\lambda, \bar{w}}^t$ where λ is the set of vertices in the graph component and \bar{w} is its set of edge weights. The strength and unity of the corresponding qualia-state is then determined not only by the connected qualia contained in the graph component, but also by the edge weights between them.

Several qualia-states may coexist at time t ; they are necessarily mutually disjoint and not functionally coupled. If the cortex is sufficiently interconnected, however, one expects one qualia-state to be much larger than the others. The cortex-wide distribution of IT neurons suggests that valenced percepts are widely distributed, although specific cortical regions might be specialized for certain percept-types or for higher intensities.

A *conscious flow* over the time interval $[t_0, t_n]$ is a temporal sequence

$$C^{[t_0, t_n]} := (C_{\lambda_0, \bar{w}_0}^{t_0}, \dots, C_{\lambda_n, \bar{w}_n}^{t_n}) \quad (17)$$

of qualia-states generated by the temporal evolution of percepts and their associated valence fields. The naturality of percept transformations, together with the sheaf-like properties of amalgamation, preserve and bind the structure of component qualia-states across successive time increments. Factors that may change the qualia-state without preserving structure include sensory inputs and changes in topology or percept-types.

Given this description, what is the ontological status of valence, qualia, and consciousness? Our position is that even an isolated nonzero valence corresponds to a minimal subjective state. At the level of qualia, a multitude of isolated qualia may be instantiated in the brain at a given time, each capturing nonzero valence and hence a subjective state.

We propose that the ordinary meaning of consciousness emerges from this initially disjoint multiplicity of elementary subjective states when there is a dominant conscious flow of relatively large qualia-states. The intensity of experience depends on the valence field intensities. The evolving sequence of qualia-states provides the scaffolding through which the valence field is organized into conscious experience.

4.5. Altered States of Consciousness

In this model, diminished consciousness, or loss of ordinary integrated consciousness, occurs when connectivity is disrupted, either at the level of qualia-states or at the level of the flow of qualia-states. The less severe disruption occurs when the flow itself becomes disconnected. For example, an interruption of processes that construct amalgamations of percepts and natural transformations between percept-types could allow qualia-states to persist, but in a temporally dissociated form. One possible example is the ketamine-induced dissociated brain state. As an NMDA antagonist, ketamine at sub-anesthetic doses inhibits the interaction between feedback and feedforward pathways (Bera et al., 2026), which may permit feedforward-generated qualia-states that are less connected with preceding qualia-states.

A more severe disruption is fragmentation of the qualia-states themselves. This would limit both the complexity of momentary consciousness and the subsequent conscious flow. Since a qualia-state results from the simultaneous realization of connected qualia, its degree of integration depends on the spatial extent of these connections. This suggests that fragmentation into many small qualia-states may appear to an external observer as catatonia or even unconsciousness, while the subject may still undergo limited conscious experience. Possible examples may include some local and global seizure states.

Another form of altered consciousness is suggested by near-death experience (NDE). In EEG studies, Borjigin et al. (2013) found that, following induced cardiac arrest in rats, feedforward and feedback connectivity in low gamma bands transiently rose for approximately thirty seconds to levels exceeding the awake state. They also reported increased phase-coupling of synchronous gamma oscillations to alpha and theta oscillations, again exceeding waking-state levels. Although the relevant neurodynamics remain under investigation, these data suggest the possibility that rapid increases in STO coherence and con-

nectivity may produce large positive valence and heightened consciousness during NDE-like states.

4.5.1. Surgical Anesthesia

Because, in this model, percepts may persist in the absence of consciousness, surgical anesthesia may require the abolition, or at least severe restriction, of the valence field throughout the cortex. In this state, qualia cannot form, even if percepts persist, because valence is absent. The proposed mechanism for abolishing the valence field is the establishment of conditions under which entropy remains nearly constant within IT pyramidal-neuron networks.

Suzuki and Larkum (2020) show that anesthetic agents decouple the apical tufts of layer 5 pyramidal (L5p) neurons from their somata and basal dendrites. These agents do so either by blocking muscarinic acetylcholine receptors (mAChRs) or by blocking thalamic activation of metabotropic glutamate receptors (mGluRs) on the apical dendrites of L5p neurons. This disconnects feedback inputs to apical tufts in layer 1 from feedforward inputs to the basal dendrites of L5p neurons. Suzuki and Larkum suggest that this unites two current theories of anesthetic-induced unconsciousness: one according to which anesthetics disrupt the processing of layer 1 feedback in cortico-cortical loops, and another according to which they disrupt higher-order thalamocortical loops. On their view, both disruptions produce unconsciousness because each decouples the apical tuft of L5p neurons from the soma.

In addition to this decoupling of L5p neurons, Bharioke et al. (2022) found that general anesthesia globally synchronizes activity selectively in L5p neurons. They report that activity within both apical and basal dendrites is synchronous, although only basal dendritic activity is temporally locked to somatic activity.

The natural interpretation in the present theory is that anesthetics, through their effects on L5p neurons, disrupt thalamic and cortico-cortical feedback pathways influencing IT neurons, thereby creating conditions under which the entropies of IT subthreshold distributions remain nearly constant, producing a null or severely restricted valence field. This does not require synchronization or desynchronization of IT neurons within their own patterns; it requires only that the entropies of those pattern distributions remain nearly constant over time.

It is notable that Bharioke et al., using Fentanyl-Medetomidine-Midazolam anesthesia, paired L2/3 IT patch-clamping with L5p GCaMP7s imaging and found the synchrony between L2/3 IT *subthreshold voltages* and mean GCaMP activity was significantly lower than the internal synchrony of L5p neurons, providing further evidence of the disabling of the L5p neurons ability to modulate IT subthreshold coherency.

4.6. Unconscious Decisions

We have modeled a decision at time t regarding a formula φ , characterizing a percept-type A , as the realization of a distribution p_D^t on a decision stage D for φ such that $D \Vdash_J \varphi(p_D^t)$ (Section 3.3.2). If A is not J -closed, then it is possible that

$D \Vdash_J \varphi(p_D^t)$ while $p_D^t \notin A(D)$. The first condition may trigger an affirmative decision regarding percept-type A at time t , while the second indicates that (D, p_D^t) is not a member of the A -state \mathcal{A}^t . Hence, (D, p_D^t) may not appear within a quale associated with percept-type A at time t , although it could still be realized as a witness for some other percept-type. Consequently, a decision may occur without conscious awareness of it being made.

5. A Neural Substrate for Valence

A role for subthreshold states beyond support for action potentials is consistent with evidence that postsynaptic and dendritic processes account for the dominant fraction of cortical signaling energy (Attwell and Laughlin, 2001; Harris et al., 2012). Moreover, pyramidal neurons spend the vast majority of their time in subthreshold dynamics rather than producing axonal output. Reframing STO dynamics as an integral organizational mechanism, rather than a mere support system for neuronal firing, suggests that valence emerges from field dynamics rather than action-potential-based computation alone. Specifically, we propose that valence corresponds to the rate of entropy change within networks of STOs among IT neurons. More generally, this valence represents an entropic shift within a space of thermodynamically distinguishable, reactive field states jointly produced by sources within a dissipative medium.

From an evolutionary perspective, Shepherd and Rowe (2017) argue that the ancestral amniote three-layer cortex, which emerged approximately 320 million years ago, was built from modules centered on intratelencephalic (IT) pyramidal neurons that supported higher cognitive functions. In mammals, IT neurons occur throughout the cortex where they are in layers 2 through 6, but are concentrated in layers 2 and 3. They are highly interconnected, communicating locally as well as across hemispheres. Moberg and Takahashi (2022) distinguish two other major classes of cortical pyramidal neurons: (i) corticothalamic (CT) neurons in layer 6, which project to the thalamus, to layer 5a IT neurons, and to interneurons; and (ii) pyramidal tract (PT) neurons in layer 5b, which project throughout the neuroaxis but influence IT neurons only indirectly, through the thalamus. They further report that the apical dendrites of IT and PT neurons exhibit distinct subthreshold responses to identical inputs, with IT neurons showing slower transfer of synaptic potentials and higher recurrent connectivity among themselves. These features suggest that IT neurons are especially well suited to support strong, dynamically changing coupling patterns between their STO states that could produce changing entropy.

5.1. Classifying Basic Processes

We name the three basic process types that have been discussed.

Type 1 processes generate the topology from limbic valence. Communication from the ACC and insula to broader cortical regions may determine what counts as a cover, and hence what local distributions are sufficient for amalgamation.

This communication could involve direct cortico-cortical projections, thalamic loops, particularly with pulvinar, mediodorsal, and intralaminar nuclei, and neuromodulation, particularly locus coeruleus noradrenergic and basal forebrain cholinergic projections (Rikhye et al., 2018; Saalman, 2014; Sara, 2009; Shackman et al., 2011; Zhao et al., 2018).

Type 2 processes manipulate percept-type handles to build logically complex handles from simpler ones. These processes, at least in hominids, could utilize subcortical structures, the lateral posterior cerebellum, and the dlPFC for handle selection, handle sequencing, and symbolic inference with handles, respectively.

Support for the role of the lateral posterior cerebellum in Type 2 processes can be summarized as follows:

- During recent hominid and early human evolution, a non-allometric expansion of the prefrontal cortex occurred in tandem with an expansion of the lateral posterior cerebellum.
- Recent research indicates the lateral posterior cerebellum in humans has extensive bidirectional connections with non-motor regions such as the prefrontal and association cortices (Schmahmann and Sherman, 1998; Middleton and Strick, 2001).
- Functional neuroimaging and comparative anatomy suggest that these posterior cerebellar regions participate broadly in cognitive and associative processing rather than purely motor control (Buckner, 2013).

Schmahmann (2000) pioneered the idea that this concurrent evolution suggests that the lateral posterior cerebellum assists in the spatiotemporal coordination of thought, analogous to the role of the older motor cerebellum in the spatiotemporal organization of movement for premotor cortex. This assessment is supported by observations of cognitive dysmetria and psychotic thinking in patients after injury to, or disease of, the posterior cerebellum.

Type 3 processes produce content: percept-types, percepts, and constructions from handles. Explanations of their neurobiological basis are beyond the scope of this work. However, Friston (2010) has developed a promising theory for percept formation based on a free-energy principle. Beck et al. (2011) have identified processes that could contribute to such constructions, such as pooling, divisive normalization, and shunting inhibition.

We also classify as a Type 3 process the construction of a natural transformation $P_\delta \rightarrow A_\delta$ between percept-types defined within the same cortical boundary (Section 1.3). This would map P_δ -percepts to A_δ -percepts on stages in δ .

6. Conclusion

We propose that animal brains have gradually evolved to approximate the principles described here with increasing fidelity. If so, the framework developed here may capture essential features of vertebrate brain function:

1. The brain can be modeled as approximating a topos equipped with a valence-induced Grothendieck topology, which modulates admissible amalgamations and governs an internal intuitionistic logic.
2. The ontic status of valence implies that it can have observable physical consequences through momentum and energy flows associated with changes in coherency within neuronal ensembles and changes in dispersion within individual neurons.
3. Logical operations on percept-types establish cortical regions whose neural parameter values support percepts with prescribed qualities.
4. An irreducible subjective state corresponding to nonzero valence is a scalar quantity representing structureless hedonic tone. Structured subjective experience emerges as a valenced percept, combining hedonic tone, structure, and quality: hedonic tone is given by valence, structure by the maximal sieve on the supporting stage D , and quality by the probability distribution p_D on the joint STO state space Σ_D . Consciousness is then identified with a temporal sequence of maximally connected valenced percepts.

Declaration of Competing Interest

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